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Effect of Adding A Commercial Broiler Feed Premix on Lipid Metabolism, Abdominal Fat Deposition, and Body Temperature

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Received Date: 09-June-2021 Accepted Date: 25-June-2021 Published Date: 30-June-2021

Abstract

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of increasing the levels of a commercial vitamin premix calfostrong® on lipid metabolism, glycemia and body temperature in broilers. A total of one hundred thirty chicks (ISA15 strain) were randomly assigned to three experimental groups: birds of Vita ++ group, were treated with an increased dose of calfostrong® during their grower period (between day 15 and day 47); birds of Vita + group were treated with an increased dose of calfostrong® during their finisher period (between day 40 and day 47). The control group was treated with another commercial vitamin premix: chicktonic®. As recommended by the manufacturer, calfostrong® was incorporated directly in the birds feed, while chicktonic® was used in the birds drinking water. On day 49, blood samples were taken in order to determine triglycerides, total cholesterol and blood sugar serum levels. At slaughter (day 50), abdominal fat and liver weights were recorded. Increasing the vitamin premix doses, starting from the grower period, reduced abdominal fat (15.18 g vs 35.33 g in Vita + group and 27g in control group) and blood sugar levels (2.34 g / l vs 2 , 30g / l in Vita + and 2.54g / l in control group). Increasing the vitamin premix doses, starting from the finisher period (Vita + group), gave the highest cholesterol level (1.71g / l vs 1, 32g / l in Vita ++ group and 1.05g / l in control group). Monitoring body temperature variations in Vita++ birds, showed the effect of calfostrong® on body temperature, with an increase in body temperature each time the dose was increased (between day 30 and day 42). On day 48, when the treatment with vitamins was stopped, body temperature decreased again.

Keywords: blood parameters, body temperature, feed premix, broiler chickens.

Introduction

Vitamins are considered as “growth factors” (Cepero and Perez, 2012; Afssa, 2000). With a few exceptions, they cannot be synthesized by the body, and must be provided by the basic diet and nutritional supplements (Desprels, 2001; Birlouez-Aragon and al., 1995 cited by Labarthe, 2012). Broilers feed consists of grains, wheat bran, and meal. Wheat grains and bran are rich in vitamins BI , B2 and PP (Godon and Lasseran, 1989 cited by Djelti, 2014; Cothenet and Bastianelli, 2003), Soybean meal is rich in choline, folic acid, riboflavin, nicotinic acid, pantothenic acid, thiamine (Javello, 2007) and vitamin E. (Cuvelier and al., 2003) However, despite the presence of vitamins in feed, certain breeding conditions can make their use and synthesis by the body insufficient (Birlouez-Aragon and al., 1995 cited by Labarthe, 2012)

such breeding conditions include: lack of exposure to sunlight; lack of dietary protein intake; a deficiency in available tryptophan and lack of endogenous synthesis of niacin. Also, prolonged broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy causes an alteration of the digestive flora and reduced synthesis of K2 and group B vitamins.

Selection in broilers for rapid growth produced changes in their thermoregulatory mechanisms, their hormonal metabolism, their digestive enzymes activity, as well as their ability to absorb nutrients. The growth rate of these chickens is higher; therefore the energy levels in their feed must increase. This justifies the need to increase vitamin supplements levels, especially those involved in the metabolism, like group B vitamins. (Cepero and Perez, 2012, Perez-Vendrel and al., 2003; Whitehead.b, 2002; Stahly and Cook, 1996 cited by Castaing and al 2003), In fact, the predominance of wheat which is very energetic rather than corn makes B vitamins supplement no longer needed, as well as niacin, biotin, pantothenic acid, and vitamin A (Whitehead, 2002).

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Vitamin B₂ (riboflavin) and Vitamin B₃ or PP (niacin) are directly involved in the metabolism of carbohydrates, amino acids and lipids. (Labarthe 2012; Combs, 2008; Eitenmiller and Lee, 2004), vitamin B₅ (pantothenic acid) is a precursor of the synthesis of the two metabolites, coenzyme A and PCA included in the Krebs cycle, it is also involved in the synthesis of fatty acids, cholesterol, and triglycerides and stimulates the production of antibodies. (Cepero and Perez, 2012; Bender, 2003)

In addition to their effect on the chickens' growth, authors have noticed the influence of feed additives, vitamins, and changes in ambient temperature on blood biochemical parameters. Many authors reported that an ambient temperature above 32 °C would cause a significant increase in rectal temperature. (Kudair and Al-Hussary, 2010; Cetin et al., 2002; Geraret, 1991)

In broiler chickens, vitamins doses are administered according to the bird's growth rate specific to each of the three rearing periods: starter, grower and finisher. According to many authors, it is strongly discouraged to reduce the doses or stop vitamin supplementation at the end of the finisher period (the last 5-7 days), because chickens are often stressed during transport to the slaughterhouse. (Whitehead 2002.b; Maiorka et al. 2002; Dehyim et al. 1995). In this experimental study, we tested the effect of calfostrong® a commercial vitamin premix incorporated directly in the broilers feed. The premix levels were increased starting either from the animals' grower period or during their finisher one. The effect of this vitamin premix was also compared with another vitamin premix, chicktonic®, distributed in the broilers drinking water. Parameters such as triglycerides, cholesterol, blood sugar, and body temperature were used to compare the different vitamin supplementation protocols.

Materials and methods

Birds

All procedures used in this experiment were approved by the scientific council of the Institute of Veterinary Sciences (University of Constantine, Algeria) and are conform to international guidelines concerning animal care and use in research and teaching (NIH publications no 85-93 revised 1985). A total of 130 one-day-old male chicks of ISA 15 strain, were purchased from a local hatchery located in Sétif province (Eastern Algeria). The ISA 15 strain is one of the most bred broiler strain in the region. Mostly due to: its zootechnical performances, its high resistance against diseases, its low mortality rate and its adaptation to different breeding conditions. Upon their reception chicks were weighed and randomly assigned to the different experimental groups. Standard management practices of commercial broiler production were applied. The chicks were vaccinated against gumboro disease and Newcastle disease at the appropriate ages.

Housing

For the duration of the study (from day1 to day 50), the birds were housed in an experimental poultry house with a controlled environment regarding: ventilation, humidity, temperature, hygiene and sanitary requirements. The 12.5 m² living area of the facility was divided into three separate pens, to receive each experimental group. The heating was provided by two gas radiators with a capacity of 100 chicks. Towards the end of the grower period, one radiant was removed, keeping only one radiant for the finisher period. The first week (day 1 to day 7), the average recorded temperature was 31, 30 °C (morning) and 34.61 °C (afternoon). As the animals grow, temperatures were gradually decreased, to reached on the last week (day 41 to day 49), an average of 19.25 °C (morning) and 22.17 °C (afternoon). From day 1 to day 49, humidity levels approached the standards (45% - 65%) indicated in the Cobb broiler breeding guide (2010). They were included in the range [40.8% - 69%] in the morning and [54% -70%] in the afternoon.

Diet

Birds were provided standard starter (day1 to day15); grower (day16 to day 45) and finisher (day 46 to day 50) diets. Feed provided by a local producer, was based on: corn, soybeans, and wheat bran, without additional vitamins. All diets had been formulated to cover appropriately, the birds' energy and protein requirements during the three periods of breeding with energy levels (sugar and lipids) of: 32.21% in the starter period, 37.56% in the grower period, and 47.75% in the finisher one. Its protein value is close to 18% in the starter and grower periods, and 17% during the finisher one.

Daily feed consumption

Daily feed consumption per experimental group was calculated by measuring the quantities provided for feeding and the leftover quantities.

Individual Feed Intake grams / day (IFI) was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\text{IFI (g)} = \frac{\text{Quantity of distributed feed (g) / period} - \text{Quantity of refused feed (g) / period}}{\text{Duration of period} \times \text{number of subjects}}$$

Treatments

All used drugs are produced by INVESA (International industrial Veterinaria, S.A., Spain)

All treatments were withdrawn, 24 hours before slaughter.

Calfostonic®: is a complete mix of trace elements (iron, copper, zinc, cobalt, potassium, calcium, phosphate) and vitamins (vitamin C absent), contains seven 7 acids (choline, methionine, lysine, carnitine, nicotinic acid, panthotenate and glutamate) as well as gentian root. It was added to the daily feed ration, just before the feed is distributed to the birds.

Chicktonic® : is a liquid form complex of hydro and fat-soluble vitamins, which contains in addition 6 amino acids composing Calfostonic® (AA carnitine absent), arginine , aspartame and biotin.

Betamint®: As a standard management practice, all animal received also a commercial antis tress, which is a mentholated oral solution, used in drinking water to alleviate dehydration symptoms associated with heat stress, and to improve metabolism in poultry. This product contains vitamin C (90g/L), and other nutrients such as betaine, electrolytes, menthol and sweeteners .

Experimental design

Birds were randomly assigned to three experimental groups:

Control group (30 chicks): birds of this group received chicktonic® and Betamint® with dosages and duration of treatment as applied by many farmers of the region; this group is considered as control (table 01).

(Vit ++) group (50 chicks): birds of this group were treated with an increased dose of calfostonic® starting from their grower period (between day 15 and day 47)

(Vit +) group (50 chicks): birds of this group were treated with an increased dose of calfostonic® starting from their finisher period (between day 40 and day 47) (table 2) . .

Table 1: Chicktonic® and Betamint® dosages and duration of treatment (Control group).

Period of administration	Total days of treatment	
	Chicktonic (1m/l)	Betamint (1m/l)
day1to day12	5 days	6 days
day13 to day 29	8 days	14 days
Day 30 to day 43	6 days	9 days
		3 days
Day 44 to day 47	5 days	5 days

Table 2: Calfostonic® dosages and duration of treatment

Period of administration	Vita+ group*		Vita++ group*	
	dose	Total day of treatment	dose	Total days of treatment
day1to day14	1g/Kg	7 days	1g/Kg	10 days
day 15 to day 29	1g/Kg	14 days	2 g/Kg	12 days
day 30 to day41	1g/Kg	6 days	2,5 g/Kg	10 days
	2,5 g/Kg	2 days		
Day 42to day 47	2,5 g/Kg	6 days	3,5 g/Kg	5 days

*: betamint : total days of treatment are similar at the control group .

Abdominal fat deposition and liver weight

Samples of 30% birds were taken from each group. After recording their live weight, birds were sacrificed, defeathered and eviscerated , the obtained carcasses were immediately weighted (hot carcasses), the fat covering their abdominal parts (around the cloaca) as well as their livers were collected and weighed.

Blood parameters

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On day 49, five chickens from each group were slaughtered, the blood from their jugular vein was collected in heparinized polystyrene tubes. Blood samples were immediately sent to the laboratory to separate the serum and analyze the following biochemical parameters: glycemia, total cholesterol, and triglycerides.

Body temperature

In order to study the effect of increasing the dose of vitamins on body temperature, 10 birds from the Vita ++ group were randomly selected and their rectal temperature was recorded using a digital thermometer. Body temperature was recorded at 30, 36, 42, and 48 days of age, before feed distribution (9 a.m.) and 4 hours afterwards, (around 1:30 p.m).

Statistical analysis

Data were analyzed using statistical software Stata 2018 (StataCorp LP). Means were compared using ANOVA (one way analysis of variance). Correlation and covariance tests between the three analyzed blood parameters were analyzed. The linear regression curves (lowess type) were drawn by this same software, Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant.

Results

Triglycerides and total cholesterol levels

Birds treated with increasing calfostronic® levels starting from their grower period (group Vita ++), showed a significantly (>0.05) higher serum triglycerides mean levels (1.65 ± 0.53 g / l) compared with animals treated during their finisher period (1.30 ± 0.31 g / l) or those treated with the standard chicktonic® vitamin premix distributed in drinking water (1.05 ± 0.25 g / l).

On the other hand, total cholesterol was significantly lower (1.32 g / l), in Vita ++ group birds compared with (Vita + group) (1.71 ± 0.12 g / l). The Pearson correlation coefficient showed a positive correlation (66.69%) between triglycerides and total cholesterol in the Vita ++ group (table 4).

Abdominal fat deposition and liver weight

Increasing the dose of calfostronic® starting from the grower period (group Vita ++), resulted in the lowest abdominal fat deposition (15.18 g) and the highest liver weight (60.06 g).

While the increase in the dose starting from the finisher period (Vita + group), gave a higher fat deposit (35.33 g) with a lower liver weight (49.66 g).

chicktonic® birds showed liver weights close to those recorded in the (Vita + group) (43.5 g), but their abdominal fat deposition was lower (27 g) (table 3).

Blood sugar levels

In both calfostronic® groups (Vita ++ and Vita +) blood sugar levels were significantly lower, than those recorded in chicktonic® group. With values of, 2.30 g / l in the Vita + group and 2.34 g / l in the Vita ++ group, in comparison with (2.54 g / l) recorded in the control group (Table 3).

In the Vita ++ group, The Pearson correlation coefficient showed a positive correlation (89.04%) between blood sugar and triglycerides levels. While in the Vita + group, the correlation coefficients was negative between these two parameters. Also in the Vita + group, the correlation coefficients between glycemia and cholesterol levels was negative (Table 4).

Blood sugar levels depend on the feed intake during the two days before the blood analysis (from Day 47 to Day 49) (Table 5). Indeed, during this period, chickens in the two calfostronic® groups (Vita ++ and Vita +) consumed less feed compared to the control group (Table 5).

Table 3: Effect of the three vitamin complementation protocols on triglycerides, cholesterol, blood sugar, liver weight and abdominal fat deposition.

Parameters	Experimental groups		
	Control (n : 10)	Vita+ (n : 15)	Lot Vita++ (n : 15)
Serum triglycerides (g / l)	1.05 ± 0.25 ab	1.30 ± 0.31 ab	1.65 ± 0.53 a
Serum cholesterol (g / l)	1.05 ± 0.08 ab	1.71 ± 0.12 a	1.32 ± 0.25 ab
Blood sugar (g / l)	2.54 ± 0.57 a	2.30 ± 0.09 ab	2.34 ± 0.19 ab
Abdominal fat deposition (g)	27 ± 6.32 a	35.33 ± 10.26 a	15.18 ± 8.28
Liver weight (g)	43.5 ± 3.37 *	49.66 ± 7.19 *	60.06 ± 11.04 *

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Identical letters on the same line indicate that the differences are significant with the ANOVA test at the threshold α : 0.05. *: bartlett test significant at the α threshold: 0.05.

Table 4: Correlations between triglycerides, cholesterol and glycemia.

Blood parameters	Pearson correlation coefficient (%)		
	Control (n : 10)	Vita+ (n : 15)	Lot Vita++ (n : 15)
Cholesterol / triglycerides	0,9592 (95,92 %)	0,1201 (12,01%)	0,6669 (66,69 %)
Blood sugar / triglycerides	0,3394 (33,94 %)	- 0,4045 (40,45 %)	0,8904 (89,04 %)
Blood sugar / cholesterol	0,3052 (30,52 %)	- 0,8687 (86,87%)	0,3487 (34,87 %)

Table 5: Individual Feed Intake (g /day) during the finisher period

Age in days	Control	Vita+	Vita++
40	222,51	253,69	205,83
41	234,83	280,12	211,79
42	251,38	281,50	238,10
43	379,31	269,76	261,90
44	275,86	206,90	309,52
45	349,66	273,81	286,07
46	268,97	257,14	190,48
47	299,48	249,52	190,00
48	410,34	285,71	214,29
49	0,00	0,00	0,00
Day 40 to day 49	2692,334	2358,16	2107,97

Body Temperature variations in Vita ++ group

The birds' body temperatures before feed distribution vary in the interval [37.50 ° C- 41.10 ° C]. Four hours after feed distribution, body temperatures increase, with values in the range of [39.30 ° C to 41.40 ° C]. Tables 6 and 7, show the mean, minimum and maximum values of body temperatures, recorded at each age. Fig. 1, shows that before feed distribution, on average the body temperature recorded at d30 is 40.86 ° C, it decreased by -0.53 ° C after feed distribution. After ingestion and digestion, the temperature values increased between day 36 and 48 by (+ 0.27 ° C, + 1.85 ° C and + 0.22 ° C), However, these differences are not significant.

There is a negative correlation between age and body temperature before feeding, Pearson's coefficient is - 0.52 (52%), after this correlation is almost zero 0.02 (2%).

Fig1. Variation in body temperature before and after vitamin supplementation

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Table 6: Body temperature (°C) before premix distribution (at 9 a.m)

Age in days	Mean ± standard deviation	minimum	maximum	ANOVA (P value : $\alpha > 0,05$)	Equality of variance test * [Confidence interval - 95%]
30	40,86±0,13	40,60	41,10	NS	[40,76-40,96]
36	40,38±0,58	39,20	41	NS	[39,96-40,80]
42	38,83±1,00	37,50	40,40	NS	[38,11-39,54]
48	40,21±0,32	39,60	40,60	NS	[39,98-40,44]

NS : not significant - * :hypothesis H0 :0 accepted.

Table 7: Body temperature (°C) 4 hours after feed distribution (at 13:30 p.m)

Age in days	Mean ± standard deviation	minimum	maximum	ANOVA (P value : $\alpha > 0,05$)	Equality of variance test * [Confidence interval - 95%]
J30	40,33	39,30	41,2	NS	[39,93-40,73]
J36	40,65	39,50	41,4	NS	[40,24-41,05]
J42	40,68	40,30	41,3	NS	[40,48-40,88]
J48	40,43	39,60	41,1	NS	[40,11-40,74]

NS : not significant - * :hypothesis H0 :0 accepted.

The effect of calfostronic® on body temperature is shown in fig. 2. Increasing the vitamin dose (between day 30 and day 42), lead to an increase in body temperature. On day 48, when vitamin treatment is stopped (dose 0), the temperature decreases again. The Pearson coefficient of 0.69 (69%) shows a positive correlation between calfostronic® dose and body temperature, Theoretically, Feed consumption and ambient temperature, both influence heat production in birds, but in our experience, The two curves (fig3 and 4) of linear regression between body temperature and these two parameters: feed consumption and ambient temperature, do not show the direct effect of these two parameters on body temperature, as is the case for the dose effect. In fact, the calculated Pearson correlation coefficients are low, their respective values are: 0.40 (40%) and 0.06 (6%).

Fig2. Variation in body temperature depending on calfostronic® dose.

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Fig3. Body temperature variation depending on feed consumption.

Fig4. Body temperature variation depending on ambient temperature.

Discussion

Lipid metabolism

Increasing calfostronic®, intake during the finisher period (Vita ++ group) from (1g / kg) to the doses of (2 g / kg ; 2.5g / kg and 3.5 g / kg), did not affected the birds’ lipid metabolism. Animals of this experimental group showed the best lipid profile in comparison with the chicktonic® control group and the Vita + group receiving the increase of calfostronic®, dosage during the grower period. Recorded serum triglycerides level (1.65g / l) was close to the ISA15 strain standard level (1.60g / l) (Idoui et al., 2009). According to Basmacioglu and Ergul, (2005), in general triglycerides levels in broilers, can be ≤ 1.50g / l. Mean total cholesterol levels correspond perfectly to the ISA15 standard (1.32g / l) (Idoui et al., 2009). According to (Hochleithner, 2013) Total cholesterol levels in broiler chickens can be even higher, varying between 2.27 g / l and 3 g / l.

Increasing vitamin premix starting from day 40 (from 1g / kg, 2 g / kg to 2.5g / kg), favored an increase in total cholesterol (1.71g / l) and the deposition of abdominal fat (35, 33g / l), however this deposit corresponds to the ISA15 standard .

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Triglyceride level (1.30g / l) is lower than the norm. In chickens, during the finisher period, researchers observed an exponential increase in fat deposition. (Braun and Sweazea, 2008; Buyse et al. 2004; Riesenfeld et al., 1982). In the finisher period, Perez et al (2003) found that, even with vitamin treatment, abdominal fat deposition was more or less important under the conditions of feed enriched with a vitamin complex of optimum level OVNtm, i.e. 41, 71g vs 47.14g in the control group.

The highest liver weight was recorded in the Vita ++ group, with an average weight of 60.06g vs 43.5g in the control group). Hassan, and Leclercq (1972), obtained a liver weight of 60.40g, with feed (corn gluten) supplemented with choline and lysine .In the Vita + group, the average weight obtained (49.66 g) is higher than in the control group, but significantly lower than in the Vita ++ group .

The liver is the site of lipid metabolism regulation. After their absorption into the enterocyte, the short-chain fatty acids are esterified there into triglycerides (Kerr et al., 2015) .These are associated with cholesterol, cholesterol esters, phospholipids and certain proteins and form a complex called lipoprotein or chylomicrons (called portomicrons in birds) which will pass from the intestine into the lymph and then join the bloodstream in order to be taken up by the tissues. In broilers, lipogenesis takes place mainly in the liver (Leveille et al., 1975), while lipolysis takes place in adipocytes under the effect of lipases present in the cytoplasm of these cells. In broilers, the most important fatty tissue is the one deposited in the abdomen. The fatty acids released by this route can be used by other cells in the body as a source of energy (Gardan, 2007). The calfostronic premix is rich in B vitamins group and amino acids. B vitamins: B1 (thiamine), B 2 (riboflavin) B3 or PP (niacin) and B5 (pantothenic acid) are directly involved in carbohydrates metabolism, amino acids and lipids. (Labarthe 2012; Combs, 2008; Bender, 2003). Niacin and Vitamin B5 are involved in the synthesis of fatty acids, triglycerides, steroid hormones and cholesterol. (Cepero and Perez, 2012; Eitenmiller and Lee, 2004).

According to Hassan, and Leclercq (1972), nutritional factors (minerals, vitamins or amino acids) can prevent hepatic steatosis by allowing the mobilization of fats to the periphery through transferring triglycerides to the bloodstream. According to these authors, a supply of amino acids seem essential to allow the liver to show a high synthetic activity, and to maintain a cellular structure compatible with lipid overload. Besides their use for protein synthesis, amino acids, glutamine and histidine can be used for glucose synthesis.

Fat chickens strains have a higher circulating betaine concentration and methionine level and lower circulating glutamine and histidine levels than the lean strains. These results suggest an involvement of methionine metabolism in the variation of fat mass in chickens (Basmacioglu and Ergul, 2005). According to Attia et al. (2017) a diet with low methionine and lysine content can lead to a decrease in total serum proteins, total plasma lipids, triglycerides, and cholesterol. Larbier and Leclercq (INRA, 1992) reported that excess amino acids decrease lipogenesis. Rabie and Szilagy (1998) supplemented broilers feed with 50 mg per kg of L-carnitine, which resulted in a decrease in the amount and percentage of abdominal fat.

In 2007, Skiba-Cassy et al. found that when fed, the liver of lean chickens show higher hepatic levels of carnitine palmitoyltransferase1 and mRNA expressions and the enzyme β -hydroxyacyl-CoA dehydrogenase compared to the liver of fatty chickens. These authors found a positive correlation between abdominal fat and cholesterol and plasma LDL levels; and a negative correlation with triglycerides level. In our study, we found a positive correlation between triglycerides and cholesterol, but only in the Vita ++ group and the control group.

Calfostonic® premix, also contains trace elements, it has been reported that a high dietary intake of Cu influences the levels of circulating cholesterol, as well as its muscular levels. These levels respectively decrease by 12 and 20% in chicken fed with a diet containing 250 mg / kg of Cu (Bakalli et al., 1995). This decrease results from the decrease in the hepatic concentration of glutathione peroxidase induced by a high level of copper (Kim et al 1992; NYS, 2001)

Blood sugar

Increasing Calfostonic® premix doses in feed, whether starting from day 15 or from day 40, led to a drop in feed consumption and blood sugar levels, 2.30 g / l in the Vita + group and

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2, 34g / l in the Vita ++ group, in comparison with (2.54 g / l) recorded in the control group. For the three experimental groups, obtained levels remained within the range of the usual values for basal glycemia [1.52g / -5g / l] in broilers. Reported values of glycemia in the literature are very different from study to another and depend on the breeding conditions: 1.52-1.82 g / l (fontaine, 1992), 1.80 g / L (Suchint Simaraks, 2004), 2-5 g / L (Campbell, 2004), 2.93 g / l (Calislar and Aydin, 2006), 1.84 g / l (Kudair and Al-Hussary, 2010), 1.90 g / l (Nwaoguikpe, 2010), 2.27-3 g / l (Hochleithner, 2013) and 2.56 g / l (Amirabdollahian et al., 2014).

Tawfeek et al. (2014) found an increase in basal blood sugar (2.80g / l) in chickens submitted to heat stress conditions compared to those raised in thermal neutrality (2.14g / l). These authors obtained a decrease in blood sugar (2.44g / l) when the chickens were supplemented with a combination of vitamin E and vitamin C, as a treatment against heat stress.

Our results showed a positive correlation between glycemia and triglycerides levels in birds receiving increased doses of Calfostonic® premix starting from day 15, and a negative correlation between glycemia and cholesterol levels in birds receiving an increased doses of the premix starting from day 40. The hydrolysis of hepatic glycogen allows the release of glucose into the blood which becomes available to be used by other organs (the brain, heart and skeletal muscles) or to be used for lipids synthesis. The adipocytes also have the capacity to take up glucose (Etherton et al. 1981), which will allow the synthesis of lipids within the adipocyte itself, and increase the amount of adipose tissue.

Rectal temperature

Between day 36 and day 48, four hours after feed distribution, the animals' body temperature increased in the Vita ++ group, by (+ 0.27 ° C, + 1.85 ° C and + 0.22 ° C).

Ain Baziz (1996) reported that normal body temperature values in broilers are between 41.2 and 42.2 ° C. According to Casanovas (2011) and Maatjens (2012), the temperature at which the energy expenditure is lowest is between 40 ° C and 40.6 ° C. Sinurat et al. (1987), reported that body temperature, plasma thyroid hormone concentrations and T3 / T4 ratio vary according to the nycthemeron and depending on age, sex, sexual maturity, nutritional status animals and rearing temperature (Sinurat et al 1987, Reported by DEBasilio and PICARD,2002).

In our study, we found a positive correlation, between calfofostonic® premix dose and body temperature (Pearson coefficient of 69%). This vitamin premix is rich in amino acids, the excess intake of amino acids leads to increased catabolism and therefore greater heat production. (Geraret, 1991). In our study, low correlation coefficients were found between feed consumption and body temperature 0.40 (40%), and between ambient temperature and body temperature (0.06 (6%)).

In Ross 308 broilers which received different doses of vitamin D (2,500, 3,000, 3.5000), body temperature decreased according to the administered dose, the recorded values were: 41.06 ° C, 41, 04 ° C, 41.02 ° C. (Faria et al., 2001).

Conclusion

Increasing the dose of the calfofostonic®vitamin premix in broilers feed, starting from the grower period has a positive effect on lipid metabolism leading to a balance between triglycerides and total cholesterol levels, and a significant decrease in abdominal fat deposition. This last result is highly desirable by consumers who prefer lean broiler meat.

Increasing the dose of the vitamin premix according to our protocol did not decrease cholesterol levels which seem to be closely correlated with abdominal fat deposition.

Increasing the dose of the vitamin premix calfofostonic® starting from the grower period or only from the finisher period, led to a drop in feed consumption which is favourable to a drop in basal blood sugar, the latter was found to be correlated with triglycerides plasma levels.

The richness of calfofostonic® in amino acids and group B vitamins, which are involved in lipids and proteins metabolisms, led to an increase in body temperature, which decreased once the vitamin treatment was interrupted. Suggesting the need to monitor variations in rearing temperatures, when vitamin supplements are added to feed or probably to the drinking water.

In conclusion, a slightly higher intake of group B vitamins, amino acids and minerals in broilers feed starting with their grower period is a favourable practice to obtaining meat rich in vitamins and less fat. Since these substances contribute to the balance of lipid metabolism. A possible study of the effect of these vitamins on adipose tissue in chicken or turkey meat may complement our results.

Acknowledgements

My thanks goes to my colleague Dr. Abdeljalil Med cherif for the translation of this article and his valuable advice . I also thank my colleague Dr. Saber Beghoul who have helped us in the follow up of experimental breeding , as well as Mer brerhi elhacene , a director of ISV (constantine veterinary institute) which has always supported and anabled scientific work to be carried out within our institute.

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